

Social

SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

N. Dhana Baggiyam^{*1}, Mrs. Pankajam. R²

^{*1} M.A., MPhil, BEd., MEd Scholar, RVS College of Education, India

² M.Sc., M.Sc (Psy), M.Phil, M.Ed., M.Phil, (Edu), Assistant Professor in Physical Science, RVS
College of Education, India

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Abstract

The paper is an attempt to find the relationship between Social Intelligence and academic achievement of the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level. In the present study survey method was used. The investigator adopted the survey method to study the relationship between Social Intelligence and academic achievement Investigator selected only 300 arts group students at Higher Secondary level as sample in Coimbatore district using stratified random sampling. The findings reveal that there is a mild positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level.

Keywords: Social Intelligence; Academic Achievement; Education.

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1. Introduction

Since social intelligence was formally introduced by John Dewey in 1909, the concept has been defined and repeatedly redefined by researchers. Tests such as the George Washington Test of Social Intelligence attempted to measure social intelligence, but ultimately received widespread criticism in its validity (Cronbach, 1960). Today, social intelligence is understood as a multidimensional construct that can be accurately measured, given the right instrument for the right population (Grieve & Mahar, 2013; Silvera et al., 2001).

Recent literature contains many studies pertaining to social intelligence, many of which focus on the benefits of social intelligence or the problem associated with a lack of social intelligence. Among a sample of the many benefits suggested by research findings, social intelligence helps individuals function in a social group, secure social advancement, achieve work satisfaction, and enter and

maintain intimate relationships or friendships (Joseph & Lakshmi, 2010); plays a significant role in determining one's resilience, which is inversely related to suicidal thoughts and behaviors (Palucka, Celinski, Salmon, Schermer, 2011); relates to positive psychological health (Hooda et al., 2009). When social intelligence is less narrowly defined, the associated benefits multiply.

The growing field of neuroscience has prompted researchers to look at social intelligence from a new perspective and offer empirical explanations not available to their predecessors. Goleman and Boyatzis (2008) explain social intelligence's relationship to leadership by looking at specific structures in the brain found to be associated with empathy, which is a key part of social intelligence. According to Goleman (2007), neuroscience does offer support to the idea that humans are "wired" to connect and that neuroscience tells us that the brain is designed¹ to be social. Regarding culture and social intelligence, most of the literature in this area recognizes that specific behaviors that might contribute to social intelligence in one culture can detract from one's perceived social intelligence in another culture (Habib, Saleem, & Mahmood, 2013), although the general concept of social intelligence remains fairly stable across cultures. Social intelligence is one of many different types of intelligences that have been studied in the last several decades. Others are (a) general intelligence; (b) emotional intelligence (Goleman, 2007); (c) social-emotional intelligence (Arghode, 2013; Bar-On, 1985; Emmerling & Boyatzis, 2012; Seal, Boyatzis, & Bailey, 2006); (d) cultural intelligence (Earley & Ang, 2003); (e) "multiple" intelligences (Gardner, 2011); and "successful" intelligence (Sternberg, 1999). While some of these intelligences are related to social intelligence, and some comprise social intelligence, researchers have concluded that social intelligence is different enough from other intelligences to stand as a valid construct on its own (Crowne, 2013; Ford & Tisak, 1983; Goleman, 2007; Sternberg, 1999). Beyond intelligence, there are many related concepts and terms that are part of social intelligence used in the literature.

2. Research Design

The study aimed to identify the learning difficulties in English as a second language among ninth standard students. In the present study survey method was used. The investigator adopted the survey method to study the relationship between Social Intelligence and academic achievement. Investigator selected only 300 arts group students at Higher Secondary level as sample in Coimbatore district using stratified random sampling.

Hypothesis: 1

There will be a difference in Social Intelligence among arts group students at higher secondary level.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage difference in social intelligence among arts group students at the Higher Secondary level

SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE								
Low			Moderate			High		
Q1	F	%	Q2	F	%	Q3	F	%
202	91	30.33%	211	109	36.33%	219	100	33.33%

The above table exhibits the result of the difference in social intelligence among arts group students at higher secondary level. According to the table totally 30.33% of arts group students at higher secondary level belong to low level of social intelligence, 36.33% arts group students at higher secondary level belong to moderate level of social intelligence, and 33.33% of arts group students at higher secondary level belong to high level of social intelligence.

Hypothesis: 2

There will be a difference in academic achievement among the arts group students at Higher Secondary School level.

Table 2: Frequencies and percentage difference in academic achievement among arts group students at the Higher Secondary level

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT								
Low			Moderate			High		
Q1	F	%	Q2	F	%	Q3	F	%
960	76	25.33%	1029	150	50%	1137	74	24.66%

The above table exhibits the result of the difference in the academic achievement among arts group students at higher secondary level. According to the table totally 25.33% of higher secondary school students belong to low level of academic achievement, 50% of higher secondary students belong to moderate level of academic achievement, 24.66% of higher secondary students belong to high level of academic achievement.

Hypothesis 3:

There will be a significant relationship between Social Intelligence and academic achievement of the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level.

Table 3: Relationships between Social Intelligence and academic achievement of the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level

Variables	N	'r' Value
Social intelligence	300	0.14
Academic achievement	300	

The above table shows the relationship between social intelligent and academic achievement of the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level. According to this table the correlation value of class room climate and social intelligence is 0.140 which implies that that there is a mild positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level.

3. Conclusion

The findings reveal that there is a mild positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among the selected arts group students at Higher Secondary level. Also it is found that the students belonging to the moderate level of social intelligence is slightly more than the students belonging to the high level of social intelligence and students belonging to the low level of social intelligence

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